

THE IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES IN HOTEL INDUSTRY

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Abstract:

This research paper is an exploratory study based on literature review, on training programs within the hotel industry. The information gathered and discerned in this paper will explore the training needs of the employees in hotel industry and will give an insight on effectiveness of training and development in hotel industry. Since all employees need training and development no matter what industry they are in, other industries' insights may offer new perspectives to the hotel industry. Another constraint in this paper is the term training to encompass both training and development. Training is the activities that are designed to provide learners with the knowledge and skills needed for their present jobs whereas development is the learning that goes beyond today's job and has a more long-term focus. Although training and development usually go hand in hand, they differ in that training can be done by all staff, whereas development is usually undertaken by the trainee's supervisors or managers. Training also tends to be more specific while development looks more at the long-term professional goals. The trainer will teach specific skills and knowledge to the trainee in order to obtain specific goals for their present position. During the development process, staff will meet with their supervisor and or manager to discuss their strengths and weaknesses, and how to improve work performances to help expand and broaden their current career path. This paper critically examines the importance of training and development and their importance to an organization's success.

Key Words: *Training, Development, Training Needs, Hospitality.*

1. Introduction

1.1 Training

Training is concerned with imparting specific skills for a particular purpose. Training is the sequence of learning a sequence of programmed behavior. Training is the act of increasing the skills of an employee for doing a particular job.

“Training is the process that provides employees with the knowledge and the skills required to operate within the systems and standards set by management.” (Sommerville 2007)

1.2 Development

Management development is all those activities and programme when recognized and controlled have substantial influence in changing the capacity of the individual to perform his assignment better and in going so all likely to increase his potential for future assignments. Thus, management development is a combination of various training

programme, though some kind of training is necessary, it is the overall development of the competency of managerial personal in the light of the present requirement as well as the future requirement. Development an activity designed to improve the performance of existing managers and to provide for a planned growth of managers to meet future organizational requirements is management development.

Conventional 'training' is required to cover essential work-related skills, techniques and knowledge, and much of this section deals with taking a positive progressive approach to this sort of traditional 'training'.

Importantly however, the most effective way to develop people is quite different from conventional skills training, which let's face it many employees regard quite negatively. They'll do it of course, but they won't enjoy it much because it's about work, not about themselves as people. The most effective way to develop people is instead to enable learning and personal development, with all that this implies.

So, as soon as you've covered the basic work-related skills training that is much described in this section - focus on enabling learning and development for people as individuals - which extends the range of development way outside traditional work skills and knowledge, and creates far more exciting, liberating, motivational opportunities - for people and for employers.

Rightly organizations are facing great pressure to change these days - to facilitate and encourage whole-person development and fulfillment - beyond traditional training.

1.3 Need for Training

1. Globalization
2. Need of leadership.
3. Increased value placed on intangible assets & human capital.
4. Focus on link to business strategy
5. Customer's services & quality emphasis.
6. New technology.
7. High performances model at work system.
8. Economic changes.
9. Attracting & retaining talent.

Training Needs Assessment

Need Assessment also known as needs analysis; a method of analyzing how employee skill deficits can be addressed through current or future training and professional development programs, as well as determining the types of training/development programs required and how to prioritize training/development. Needs assessment is also the identification of the gap(s) between optimal performance and actual performance (Breiter & Woods, 1997, p 88).

Training Needs Analysis (TNA) is the key to reshaping the future of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Programmed in the all industries and educational institutes. It is the major component of training programmers. It is a crucial component of learning for ascertaining both the needs of the learners and the organization and as such it provides a fundamental link with relevant and effective teaching and learning process. It determines and identifies the existence of a gap between what is required of a person to perform their duties competently and what they actually know as a basis for initiating corrective measures and or remedial education. Training Needs Analysis can be an overwhelming process. It is a method that will bridge the gap between the required performance and the actual performance. It is also a method of determining whether a training need exists, and if it does, what training is required to fill the gap.

The essence of TNA is to find out the general areas of work/ healthcare where an improvement is needed that would require CPD. It focuses on identifying needs of the target audience, developing a rationale for a training programme, identifying needed inputs, determining program content and setting program goals.

To make Continuing Professional Education programmes more effective, TNA should be done before designing and conducting any training or workshops and to look into the needs of the organization, job performance and the staff. If training is the chosen solution to address those needs, it is important to first know the nature of the problem. Without that clarification, training can accomplish absolutely nothing except wasting time, efforts and resources. A training programme must be carefully planned and organized and based on needs analysis.

2. Hotel Industry

The standards of facilities and services offered have evolved over the last decade towards the extensive use of technology, environment friendly services, pricing, market segmentation, regional preferences, etc. The Indian hotel industry has seen a significant growth in room inventory across categories from upscale luxury to limited services and, boutique and budget hotels. The occupancy and the room rates have seen continued gains both from the domestic and the international traveler in both the business and leisure segment.

With the continued growth in India's GDP, improvement in the per capita income, and increased aspirational spending, the Indian hospitality sector is expected to grow faster than most countries around the world. The inherent strength of the Indian economy has led to increased international visits to India. For foreigners, the travel time has increased to three-five days for business travel and from five days to seven-10 days for leisure travel.

The government has stepped up various reforms to accelerate the industry growth with liberalization in the regulatory framework, investment friendly schemes, extensive support for creating a world class infrastructure, initiating better air and land connectivity, incentivizing regional set-up in tier III and IV cities, exploring the untapped geographical resources.

Federation of Hotel and Restaurant Associations of India states that India currently has over 200,000 hotel rooms spread across hotel categories and guest-houses and is still facing a shortfall of over 100,000 rooms. Leading hotel brands have pepped up their investments and are in various stages of commencement of new proprieties in India, both in metro and non- metro cities. Cities such as Hyderabad, Pune, Jaipur and Chandigarh have emerged as growth markets. The emergence of these secondary and tertiary cities has led to an aggressive increase in hotel development activity, which was previously dependent in just five main cities.

Technology is used almost in every department and function to increase efficiency and standardize operations. The hotels are becoming increasingly conscious for the security of its guest. Keys Hotels launched women only floors in India with video phones in each room to ensure that the women travelers feel secured and enjoy the hospitality and amenities without any apprehension. Many international chains have added various amenities such as special hair dryers and toiletries and operate women-only lounges on the dedicated floor.

2.2 An Overview of the Training and Development in Hotel Industry

Training and development are integral to a Hotel's growth and success. Hotels can however under-train their employees by being unwilling to take the time to explain new staff tasks that need to performed.

When this unwillingness occurs, Ryan (2008) states that three scenarios may take place – the employee will not be able to help a client the way they should, the client will be left unsatisfied by the hotel's service level, and lastly the employee will become frustrated by the company and his or her service level will drop to a minimum. Studies have shown that training programs increase employee satisfaction, employee morale and employee retention, and decreases turnover and hiring rates. Training has been shown to improve knowledge and in turn knowledge improves the delivery of hospitality business-related activities. Daniels (2008) mentions in her article that in the current economic situation; companies may be tempted to cut their training budgets, but they should not however abandon training. Hotels should instead use this situation as an opportunity because training boosts morale and commitment by showing employees they are a valued and important resource. The training itself provides skills and enthusiasm to help participants provide amazing customer service. Great customer experiences lead to brand loyalty. Skills' training that equips employees with the tools to increase customer loyalty is not overhead, a cost, or a frill. Training is important as it is part of the service quality that drives the performance of hotels. Chow, Haddad and Singh (2007) found in their study of 46 hotels in San Diego that by providing training and development, the hotels' employee morale, productivity and job satisfaction improved, which in turn can improve managers' morale.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Training

It is a learning process that involves the acquisition of knowledge, sharpening of skills, concepts, rules, or changing of attitudes and behaviors to enhance the performance of employees. Training is a continuous process by which employee actually gets the knowledge and get to know how he or she can perform well in the organization. There are two basic type of training,

1. On Job training
2. Off Job training

On Job training is actually done when an employee gets the training while performing his or her assigned task. Off Job training is a type of training when employees of the organization are been called for training session to learn a task.

There are many different training and development methods. On-the-job training, informal training, classroom training, internal training courses, external training courses, on-the-job coaching, life-coaching, mentoring, training assignments and tasks, skills training, product training, technical training, behavioural development training, role-playing and role-play games and exercises, attitudinal training and development, accredited training and learning, distance learning - all part of the training menu, available to use and apply according to individual training needs and organisational training needs.

Training is also available far beyond and outside the classroom. More importantly, training - or learning, to look at it from the trainee's view - is anything offering learning and developmental experience. Training and learning development includes aspects such as: ethics and morality; attitude and behaviour; leadership and determination, as well as skills and knowledge. Development isn't restricted to training - it's anything that helps a person to grow, in ability, skills, confidence, tolerance, commitment, initiative, inter-personal skills, understanding, self-control, motivation and more.

If you consider the attributes of really effective people, be they leaders, managers, operators, technicians; any role at all, the important qualities which make good performers special are likely to be attitudinal. Skills and knowledge, and the processes available to people, are no great advantage. What makes people effective and valuable to any organization is their attitude.

Attitude includes qualities that require different training and learning methods. Attitude stems from a person's mind-set, belief system, emotional maturity, self-confidence, and experience. These are the greatest training and development challenges faced, and there are better ways of achieving this sort of change and development than putting people in a classroom, or indeed by delivering most sorts of conventional business or skills training, which people see as a chore.

This is why training and learning must extend far beyond conventional classroom training courses. Be creative, innovative, and open-minded, and you will discover learning in virtually every new experience, whether for yourself, your team, or your organization. If you want to make a difference, think about what really helps people to change.

All supervisors and managers should enable and provide training and development for their people - training develops people, it improves performance, raises morale; training and developing people increases the health and effectiveness of the organization, and the productivity of the business.

The leader's ethics and behaviour set the standard for their people's, which determines how productively they use their skills and knowledge. Training is nothing without the motivation to apply it effectively. A strong capability to plan and manage skills training, the acquisition of knowledge, and the development of motivation and attitude, largely determines how well people perform in their jobs.

2.4 The Training Process

1. Assessing the training needs
2. Planning the training
3. Carrying out the training
4. Evaluating the training

The training cycle is circular; it begins with the needs assessment. A need of training always results from the difference between an ideal expect for employees' performances and the actual performances. Trainings can also be provided for new employees to help them get familiar with the work environment and tasks etc. HR department should consider the related aspects for example job analysis, performance objectives etc.

The second step in the training cycle is the planning of the training. Planning is separated into specifying training objectives, designing training programme, selecting training methods. Training goals, training method, duration, programme structure, location and selection of trainees etc. practical problems are to be answered in the planning stage.

After successfully planning the training, the training programme should be effectively carried out following the plan. The trainer should be well prepared and skilful, and the trainees should be actively participating in the training. Evaluation of the training is an unavoidable stage in the training process, to get the feedback helps adjusting and organising future trainings. Plans for future training can be done at this stage. Evaluation is the ending stage of a training cycle but at the same time it is the basis for the new training cycle (Woods 2006).

3. Standard Operating Procedures of Training and Development in Hotel Industry

Hotel Industry believes that on-going professional education is necessary for every employee. There is great

emphasis on in-house training programmes as well as nomination to external courses. In this it has technical training for skill up gradation and behavioural/managerial training for employees to shoulder higher order responsibilities. In house-training is complemented with programmes by external trainers and sponsorship to external training programs.

3.1 Purpose of Standard Operating Procedures

The purpose of Standard Operating Procedures of the Training and Development programmes is to develop a learning organization and to ensure quantifiable returns on the investment being done on Training & Development activities.

3.2 Scope of Standard Operating Procedures

This policy aims at developing systems to ensure training is need based and driven by business and organizational requirements.

3.3 Responsibility

It is the responsibility of HR Executive to ensure implementation of this policy under the supervision of Head – HR & Personnel.

3.4 Procedure

1. The Training & Development plan shall be linked with the performance year.
2. Training programmes shall be classified broadly into four main categories viz. Induction programmes, Executive/Management Development programmes, Technical / Functional skill development programmes and, Behavioural/ Attitudinal training programmes.
3. The training need identification shall be done at the end of the performance year immediately after the performance review is over, also occur when job responsibilities changes / new equipment is introduced.
4. The training needs shall be identified through three main sources viz. Business performance, Functional performance and individual performance.
5. Business performance shall lead to identification of common training needs across departments e.g. if the business suffered due to lack of leadership or could not steer out effectively from some crisis then leadership skills and crisis management will be the required training inputs.
6. Functional performance shall lead to identification of a common training need for most employees from a particular function e.g. if there are customer complaints on quality of service from a particular department then customer management skills will be the required training input.
7. Employee performance shall lead to identification of training needs for an individual employee. e. g. if an employee could not achieve his/her goals due to lack of assertiveness then assertiveness skill will be the required training input.

8. Individual training needs can also be identified through succession planning e.g. if an employee is identified as a successor to a particular position but found to be lacking in a particular skill that is a part of the targeted position's skill set then that particular skill will be the required training input for that employee.
9. Once the training needs are identified a training calendar shall be prepared by the HR Executive comprising of employee name, training programme and approximate cost of the programme (Training budget).
10. HR Executive shall get the approval from Hotel Head and Corporate HR Head for execution of the training calendar and training budget.

3.5 Nomination for External Training programme

HR Executive shall arrange to get the list of external training agencies and their training calendar. If a suitable training programme from an external agency matches the requirement of an employee training need then HR Executive shall send the proposal to the concerned functional head for approval. After obtaining approval HR Executive shall coordinate for sending the particular employee for the selected training programme

3.6 In-House Training Programmes

If a lot of employees share a common training need then HR Executive shall arrange to conduct In-house training programme. HR Executive shall arrange to prepare a list of participants for the In-house training programme in consultation with the concerned functional heads. HR Executive shall then decide duration of the training programme and venue. HR Executive shall send a circular on the training programme giving all details to all participants with a copy to respective functional heads. At the end of the training programme all participants shall be asked to fill Feedback Form, out of total trainees attended, minimum 70% of trainees must rate above 2 (Average) in the training programme, and then it will be said as effective training.

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to identify the techniques that the hotel industry could use to maintain training and development of their employees and the methods used to evaluate training programs. We had observed that through training, employee morale and satisfaction, company productivity and service quality improved. Human resources departments should emphasize the importance of training programs to its company's success. Although training programs may be reduced or eliminated, essential must remain intact to avoid future problems. Training programs can become more innovative in times of economic instability through the use of technology and self catering programs that employees monitor themselves. Companies can also involve employees with the development of training programs to avoid unnecessary spending of training budgets. Hotels can also look at other industries for ideas when developing new training programs as a way to have a competitive advantage. Hotels should also develop training programs with its business objectives, core values and strategic goals in mind. Lastly, to ensure the success of training programs in the hotel industry, programs should be evaluated regularly to monitor the Success of the programs. Human Resources Departments should emphasize the importance of training programs to its company's success.

Although training programs may be reduced or eliminated, essential must remain intact to avoid future problems.

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